

The Inclusion criteria and defining patients with PASC. Patients in the N3C database with a COVID index date defined by either a positive COVID test or a COVID Diagnosis that is linked to an ED or inpatient stay are considered for this analysis. Furthermore, patients must have follow-up at least 90 days after their COVID index visit. There was no end date enforced. These criteria, applied to the v61 N3C data release from January 27, 2022 resulted in a study population of 1,133,014 patients from 62 data contributing sites.

A previously described machine learning approach was used to define patients with PASC based on training labels identifying patients who visit long-covid clinics¹. The analyses described below applied that model training plan to subsequent data in N3C from the v61 N3C data release from January 27, 2022.

Query # 2: Objective outcomes in PASC.

Do we see increased indicators of inflammation or other objective laboratory measurements in PASC patients compared to COVID-resolved patients?

Methods: Using the above-described inclusion criteria, we separated qualified COVID-positive patients into two groups based on their model-assigned PASC status. Concept sets were created and validated previously for multiple lab values hypothesized to be associated with PASC². Units were harmonized among these respective lab measurement categories, and infeasible data were discarded according to standard N3C protocols³. For each patient, measurement data are described in terms of days since the index COVID infection.

The above graph shows median patient ferritin (ng/mL) measurement values over time after initial SARS-CoV-2 infection, segmented by predicted PASC status. Measurement values were aggregated in 7-day bins. Boxes extending above and below the line graph represent the 75% and 25% percentiles, respectively. Separation in median ferritin measurements appears to begin after 14 days post-SARS-CoV-2 infection, with continued elevation compared to non-predicted

PASC status through 84 days post-infection. **Ferritin and related biomarkers may be a target for subsequent in-depth analysis.**

The above graph shows median patient c-reactive protein measurement values (mg/L) over time after initial SARS-CoV-2 infection, segmented by predicted PASC status. Measurement values were aggregated in 7-day bins. Boxes extending above and below the line graph represent the 75% and 25% percentiles, respectively. In both predicted PASC status groups, c-reactive protein levels start above normal ranges, with predicted PASC patients initially having higher median c-reactive protein levels compared to non-predicted PASC patients. Predicted PASC patients eventually reach lower median c-reactive protein levels compared to non-predicted PASC patients around 60 days post SARS-CoV-2 infection.

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The above graph shows median patient procalcitonin measurement values (ng/mL) over time after initial SARS-CoV-2 infection, segmented by predicted PASC status. Measurement values were aggregated in 14-day bins. Boxes extending above and below the line graph represent the 75% and 25% percentiles, respectively. There does not appear to be a clear difference between the two predicted PASC status groups.

The above graph shows median patient interleukin 6 measurement values (pg/mL) over time after initial SARS-CoV-2 infection, segmented by predicted PASC status. Measurement values were aggregated in 14-day bins. Boxes extending above and below the line graph represent the 75% and 25% percentiles, respectively. Comparisons between the two predicted PASC status

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groups beyond 60 days is limited by the small number of patient values available per group (<20) at those time points. However, there is a slight elevation in acute median IL 6 levels in the predicted PASC group compared to the predicted non-PASC group, followed by what may be a reduced level of median IL 6 levels at later time points. Data from additional patients, particularly at later time points after SARS-CoV-2 infection, would be necessary for further analysis.

The above graph shows median patient white blood cell count measurement values (10³/uL) over time after initial SARS-CoV-2 infection, segmented by predicted PASC status. Measurement values were aggregated in 7-day bins. Boxes extending above and below the line graph represent the 75% and 25% percentiles, respectively. In both PASC status groups, white blood cell counts initially rise after SARS-CoV-2 infection before reducing over time. While predicted PASC patients initially have higher median white blood cell counts compared to non-predicted PASC patients, the predicted PASC patients eventually reaching lower median white blood cell count compared to non-predicted PASC patients around 70 days post SARS-CoV-2 infection.

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The above graph shows median patient erythrocyte sedimentation rate (ESR) measurement values (mm/hr) over time after initial SARS-CoV-2 infection, segmented by predicted PASC status. Measurement values were aggregated in 7-day bins. Boxes extending above and below the line graph represent the 75% and 25% percentiles, respectively. Median ESR values appear slightly elevated in predicted-PASC patients as compared to predicted non-PASC patients, although the median values intertwine beyond 50 days post-SARS-CoV-2 infection.

The above graph shows median patient albumin measurement values (g/dL) over time after initial SARS-CoV-2 infection, segmented by predicted PASC status. Measurement values were aggregated in 7-day bins. Boxes extending above and below the line graph represent the 75% and 25% percentiles, respectively. While both patient groups experienced an initial drop in

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medium albumin values, the predicted PASC patient group experienced a greater drop in median albumin levels followed by a slower return to levels shared between the two patient groups.

The above graph shows median patient D-dimer measurement values (mg/L FEU) over time after initial SARS-CoV-2 infection, segmented by predicted PASC status. Measurement values were aggregated in 14-day bins. Boxes extending above and below the line graph represent the 75% and 25% percentiles, respectively. At most timepoints after SARS-CoV-2 infection, it appears that median D-dimer values are elevated in predicted-PASC patients as compared to predicted non-PASC patients.

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The above graph shows median patient aspartate aminotransferase (AST) measurement values (IU/L) over time after initial SARS-CoV-2 infection, segmented by predicted PASC status. Measurement values were aggregated in 7-day bins. Boxes extending above and below the line graph represent the 75% and 25% percentiles, respectively. Although there may be a slight elevation in median AST values in predicted-PASC patients compared to non-predicted PASC patients between 21 and 49 days after initial SARS-CoV-2 infection, the two groups do not appear to significantly differ in median values after SARS-CoV-2 infection.

The above graph shows median patient alanine aminotransferase (ALT) measurement values (IU/L) over time after initial SARS-CoV-2 infection, segmented by predicted PASC status. Measurement values were aggregated in 7-day bins. Boxes extending above and below the line graph represent the 75% and 25% percentiles, respectively. Although there may be a slight elevation in median ALT values in predicted-PASC patients compared to non-predicted PASC patients between 21 and 49 days after initial SARS-CoV-2 infection, the two groups do not appear to significantly differ in median values after SARS-CoV-2 infection.

Limitations and Future Work: While the exploratory analyses above provide some initial insights in median lab measurements between the predicted PASC and non-PASC patients, we did not test for statistically significant differences between groups at this time. Further in-depth analysis, including splitting PASC and non-PASC patients into additional patients subsets (by gender, COVID-hospitalizations status, COVID-severity, etc.) may provide additional insights, even for measurements not currently showing differences between the full predicted-PASC and predicted non-PASC groups. Additional lab measurements of interest may be pursued after harmonization of lab values are complete.

Query # 3 Differences in PASC across time and region.

Do we see differences in the relative fraction of patients that would go on to develop PASC from different eras of the pandemic, or different regions of the US?

The maps and timelines below show the fraction of study patients who meet our COVID-positive inclusion criteria (described above) that will develop PASC. In this way, each biweekly period or state is self-normalized and represents an estimate of the incidence of PASC within our included population. For states with fewer than 250 patients meeting our inclusion criteria, this fraction is not shown in order to avoid drawing underpowered conclusions from small populations. Note that since the definition of PASC used here is based on a machine learning prediction, thresholds may be adjusted and calibrated going forward to predict an overall higher or lower burden of PASC.

Geographic distribution of fraction of COVID patients who will develop PASC
For states with > 250 qualifying patients

The map shows that appreciable heterogeneity exists across the US. While there are differences, these differences are not consistent across neighboring states, suggesting that the observed trends are more likely driven by the health system practice patterns than the population of the underlying state.

In the above graph, patients whose initial COVID event coincided with a hospitalization are shown in green, while ED or outpatient visits are shown in magenta, reflecting the overall increased risk of developing PASC in hospitalized patients.

Overlaid near the x-axis are colored bar indicators of the approximate time periods that the alpha, delta and omicron viral variants became dominant in the US. We can see an initial spike in PASC, which is possibly related to the increased severity of disease and different treatment regimens experienced by patients in the early phase of the pandemic ([Bennett et al. 2021](#)). Current data is too early to describe PASC from omicron infections, however there is a slight trend towards increasing rates of PASC in recent months that coincide with the delta variant.

Limitations and Future work:

- The major limitation of these data continues to be the modest size of the training set defining the model of PASC. Training labels (long-covid clinic usage) come from four of the 69 sites considered in this analysis. As such, there are considerable heterogeneity issues between sites that will require further attention as more data become available. Future work will consider other training labels such as the emerging U09.9 diagnosis code.
- At the state level, we are limited in some capacity by sites which contribute data to N3C. To avoid conclusions drawn from small populations, we have censored some states that have few patients.
- For timeline data, we are limited in our ability to label PASC in recently-infected patients who do not yet have enough follow-up data to represent a post-acute infection period.
- These data represent a sample-of-convenience and are not meant to fully represent population dynamics within the US.

- 1 Pfaff ER, Girvin AT, Bennett TD, Bhatia A, Brooks IM, Deer RR, *et al.* Who has long-COVID? A big data approach n.d. <https://doi.org/10.1101/2021.10.18.21265168>.
- 2 Bennett TD, Moffitt RA, Hajagos JG, Amor B, Anand A, Bissell MM, *et al.* Clinical Characterization and Prediction of Clinical Severity of SARS-CoV-2 Infection Among US

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Adults Using Data From the US National COVID Cohort Collaborative. *JAMA Network Open* 2021;4:e2116901–e2116901.

- 3 Pfaff ER, Girvin AT, Gabriel DL, Kostka K, Morris M, Palchuk M, *et al.* Synergies between centralized and federated approaches to data quality: A report from the National COVID Cohort Collaborative. *J Am Med Inform Assoc* 2021. <https://doi.org/10.1093/jamia/ocab217>.